

🏠 **SCIENCE AT THE FAIR**

[Research](#) [Team](#) [Activities](#) **[Blog](#)** [News](#) [Media](#) [Publications](#)

[UAntwerp](#) > [Projects](#) > [Science at the Fair](#) > [Blog](#)

Fairground organs, X-rays and cinema: Science and technology at the funfair

6 February 2023 - Tim Overkempe

Blog

4/4/2023 - Tricksters, scammers, imposters and frauds: a tale of all times?

24/2/2023 - Exotism and politics on the big screen: Colonial magic lantern shows in Belgium

21/2/2023 - An image speaks

'Science and technology... at the fairground? The fair, that's mostly fun, right?'
When I tell friends and family about my research, this is a common reaction. And

18/10/2022 - Researching
the history of fairgrounds is
detective work

12/10/2022 - Learning from
the fairground

Spectacular science

It is important to remember that science in the nineteenth century was not only educational, but also entertaining! Think of the first moving images shown at the fairground: people were amazed and marvelled at this new visual environment. Taking photographs also grew into a true fairground attraction in the nineteenth century, resulting in a real photograph the visitor could take home as souvenir.

Probably one of the most spectacular visual attractions was X-ray photography. Research sources have shown that **X-ray photography** was very quickly introduced to the funfair as the newest attraction. Shortly after the discovery of X-rays in 1895, there were already demonstrations and prints of this new technology. In its early years, X-ray was a **serious competitor** of early film as the most popular new visual medium. Lectures, shows and demonstrations were held to present the radioactive properties of X-ray photography to the wider public.

Technological innovations

We see a similar boom with other new technologies that took hold at the fairgrounds. Of course, the practicality of certain developments made for easier transport and economization of attractions, but technological innovations were also seen as attractions in their own right. **Electric lighting**, for example, has long been explicitly mentioned on posters and advertisements as a spectacular phenomenon. In the salon-carousels, electric lighting was added to the luxurious ensemble of 'beautiful wood sculptures, mirrors and paintings' to give the fairground attraction even more

flair. Visitors were also presented with, for example, the 'Wonders of electricity' ('Les Merveilles de l'électricité') through scientific demonstrations, spectacular visual material or even theatre plays.

GRAND CIRQUE FR. LOISSET

AUJOUR'HUI MARDI 31 MARS 1868, à 7 heures du soir

Première Représentation de la reprise de : **LES**

MERVEILLES

DE L'ÉLECTRICITÉ.

Grande Pantomime en un acte, Costumes et musique analogues.

N. B. Les Merveilles de l'Électricité ont obtenu à Bruxelles pendant deux saisons d'hiver les plus grands succès, en effet il est bien rare qu'un Cirque puisse représenter une pantomime aussi compliquée, comme mise en scène, accessoires et un si nombreux personnel. **Fr. Loisset** se fait un devoir de la produire de nouveau, nulle doute qu'elle sera accueillie avec une grande faveur par le public gantois.

If you think about it, technology still plays a big role in public entertainment. Today, small roller coasters, claw machines or other mechanical attractions dominate the fairground. Light and sound also remain important: bright neon lights and fast,

cheerful and uplifting music are still used to attract the attention of visitors.

Fairground posters as a starting point

For this research I will use different types of sources. Advertisements and posters such as those presented above are one example, but I will also study newspaper reviews, personal letters or official documents. In some cases, **material remains** such as attractions and media can be interesting sources as well. Think of fairground organs, photographic equipment that was used at the funfair and the first film projectors (or cinematographs). Some of these devices are kept in the collections of museums and archives, or owned by hobbyists or private collectors.

I will therefore pay visits to archives, museums and scientific institutes, but also collaborate with private collectors and experts who are personally involved with the history of the funfair or overall fairground culture. This variety will be a challenge as well as an opportunity to explore the phenomenon of the nineteenth-century funfair

and the role of science and technology in as many ways as possible.

Find out more about my research [here](#).

Are you or do you know (private) collectors or enthusiasts of **fairground organs, carousels or general (local) fairground history**? It would be much appreciated if you could let me know so we can get in touch: tim.overkempe@uantwerpen.be.

Image copyrights (from top to bottom)

